

The Old Monastery of Baramus

Secondary source

Entered by Alexandra Konstantinidou

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North of the present Monastery of Virgin Mary of Baramūs in the Wādī al-Naṭrūn (the ancient desert of Sketis) there is a site, formerly known as Dayr Abū Mūsā al-'Aswad (Monastery of Saint Moses the Black). However, certain researchers argued that it could be identified with the Old Monastery of Baramūs. According to the hagiological tradition, this settlement was founded on the topos of the 'Two Little Strangers'. By the end of the fourth century a *laura* already existed in its environs, which is regarded as one of the earliest communities organised in the desert of Sketis. The excavations, which were carried out by a team from Leiden University (the Netherlands), under the direction of Dr. Karel C. Innemée, brought to light the remains of a monastic compound. So far, it seems that the nucleus of the compound is the church, which has been remodelled in five different phases. At the south-eastern corner of the site a square-shaped building was uncovered; it has been considered to have been a defence tower, dating back to the fourth/fifth century, namely the earlier period of the settlement. In the western part of the complex, as well as at the north-eastern corner, parts of the living quarters or cells of the monks have been discovered. The pottery finds suggest that these cells were not inhabited before the late sixth to seventh centuries. Throughout the site a ninth century destruction level is evident. This monastic complex was in existence until the sixteenth century.

Date Range: 380 CE - 1500 CE

Region: Nitria, Kellia, and Scetis

Region tags: Africa, Eastern Mediterranean

The region of the Nitrian Desert communities of Nitria, Kellia, and Scetis in the fourth and fifth centuries

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Innemée, K. C. 2000. Deir al-Baramus, Excavations at the so-called site of Moses the Black. 1994-1999, *Bulletin de la Société d'Archéologie Copte* 39, 123-135.
- Source 2: Innemée, K. C. 2005. Excavations at the site of Deir al-Baramus 2002-2005, *Bulletin de la Société d'Archéologie Copte* 44, 55-68.

– Source 3: Innemée, K. C. 2002. The Threatened Sites of the Wadi Natrun, Egyptian Archaeology (The Bulletin of the Egypt Exploration Society) 21, 33-35.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.universiteitleiden.nl/en/nvic/research/coptic-studies>

– Source 1 Description: Project

– Source 2 URL: <https://whc.unesco.org/fr/listesindicatives/1827/>

– Source 2 Description: Unesco list

– Source 3 URL: <https://scholarlypublications.universiteitleiden.nl/handle/1887/20292>

– Source 3 Description: PhD online

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Notes: Archaeological fieldwork was carried out from 1994 until 2007.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: Team from Leiden University (the Netherlands), under direction of Dr. K. C. Innemée.

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1994-2007

Notes: The monastic settlement is partially unearthed.

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Excavations at Deir al-Baramus, the Monastery of Moses the Black.

Notes: Director: Dr. Karel C. Innemée

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Body of water (as distinct from source)

– Cave

Notes: Group of saline lakes in the region. Source of natron for millenia.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Notes: Nowadays, the monastic community living in the monastery of Virgin Mary of Baramus (Dayr al-Baramus) cultivates land around the ancient monastic site.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Notes: Merely villages are built in the area, yet not in walking distance from the site.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Notes: Desert area, which is nowadays cultivated.

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: Bir Hooker village at a distance of c. 15km.

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: Small routes connecting the monasteries of the Wadi al-Natrun as well as the neighbouring villages. Not far from the Cairo-Alexandria desert road.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: Several villages in the region.

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Notes: Main church; tower (keep?); monastic cells; other structures, such as: cisterns; oven; pits; bins, etc.

A single structure

– Yes

The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

Notes: The church, the tower and the cells are rectangular in shape. Circular and oval structures exist as well (e.g. oven, hearth, lime kilns, etc.)

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: Walls; underground bin; pottery dumps, etc.

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Notes: Cluster of buildings organised around the main church.

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: The northernmost of the monasteries of the Wadi al-Natrun, which is identified with the ancient desert of Sketis.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 4 CE - 16 CE

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

Notes: Finished, and undergone alterations during different time periods.

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
– Yes

Notes: Extended destruction layer dated to the ninth century.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed
– Collapsed

Notes: Allegedly due to a raid.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:
– As the result of pillage

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:
– Human-caused accident

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
– Yes

↳ In antiquity
– More than once

Notes: Various alterations from the moment of the monastery's construction (e.g. remodelling of the main church). Expansion of the monastic complex and construction of habitation units (monastic cells). Reparation of the damages after the ninth century destruction.

↳ In modernity
– Post-Renaissance

Notes: In the 19th-20th c. (long after the abandonment of the site that took place in the mamluk times) quarrying of building material. Nowadays, cultivation of the surrounding area.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: God (Christianity)

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Saint Maximus and Domitius (according to tradition)

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– I don't know

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– I don't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Revealed by other kind of supernatural being(s) [specify]: Cherub

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

Notes: According to hagiological tradition it was after Saint Macarius the Egyptian was persecuted by the inhabitants of a village under a false accusation.

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: Vision

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Notes: There is no respective evidence.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: Cluster of adjacent cells. Tower connected with the church through corridor and staircase. Cell attached at monastery wall.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: Church at the centre of the site.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Tower. Main church.

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:
Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.
– Square meters: 450

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:
– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:
– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:
– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Sand
– No

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– No

Notes: It is deduced by the macroscopic examination of the bricks. No specimen has been analysed.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Yes

Notes: It is deduced by the macroscopic examination of the bricks. No specimen has been analysed.

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

Notes: No specimen has been analysed.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

Notes: No specimen has been analysed.

↳ Wood

– I don't know

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

Notes: No specimen has been analysed.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

Notes: No specimen has been analysed.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

–Yes [specify]: Bricks

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Saints (?)

↳ Are there humans depicted:
– I don't know
Notes: Unidentified human figures (Saints?).

↳ Are there animals depicted:
– No

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:
– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:
– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract
– Yes

↳ Floral motifs
– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy
– Yes
Notes: Inscriptions.

↳ Other [Specify]
–Other [specify]: Cross

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:
– No

↳ Are there statues present:
– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Geometric patterns

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 4 CE - 16 CE

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Saints (?), inscriptions, floral and geometric motifs.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– I don't know

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– I don't know

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– I don't know

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– I don't know

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– I don't know

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– I don't know

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– I don't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: Holy Communion.

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– I don't know

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– I don't know

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: Unknown.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: Allegedly once a week, but could have been more often.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: Orthodoxy from the Egyptian perspective ("Coptic" Orthodoxy).

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Men (monks).

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– I don't know

Notes: Egyptian. Other ethnic groups were gathered in the Wadi al-Natrun, but it is not known whether in the Old monastery of Baramus there were non-Egyptian monks.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– I don't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Monastic cells.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– I don't know

Notes: Probably.

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

Notes: Pilgrimage

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– I don't know

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– No

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– I don't know

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Pilgrimage

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Lifes of Saints. Historia Monachorum. Historia Lausiaca, etc.

↳ Are they written at this place:

– No

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– I don't know

Bibliography

General References

Reference: The Old Monastery of Baramus, Innemée, Karel C.. "Deir Al-baramus, Excavations at the So-called Site of Moses the Black. 1994-1999". *Bulletin De La Société D'archéologie Copte*, no. -39 (2000): 123-35.

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